

PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES TO EARLY FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

Barno Toshboyeva

Doctoral student at Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages
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Abstract. This article discusses the issues of organizing foreign language classes in primary school. Early learning of a foreign language is carried out mainly through play activities aimed at the development and education of the child, which socializes the child and develops his personal characteristics. However, the problem of early education has been considered for several centuries and is actively studied by modern psychologists, scientists, teachers and methodologists. However, there are special requirements for teaching a foreign language in primary school.

Keywords. Child, speech communication, psychology, language material, repetition, natural need, speech, learning, preparation, foreign language, early learning, methodology, memory, speech hearing, attention, age.

The popularity of learning English is growing every year. And more and more parents are trying to introduce their children to foreign languages from an early age. The problem of early learning is the need to find reserves in the organization of training in order not to miss and take advantage of the sensitive period of mastering a foreign language. Experimental studies indicate that after 9 years the child partially loses the flexibility of the speech mechanism. An early age is most favorable for mastering foreign languages due to a number of psychological characteristics, namely the intensive formation of cognitive abilities, quick and easy memorization of linguistic information, special sensitivity to language phenomena, and the ability to imitate.

One of the pressing problems of modern methods of teaching a foreign language is the organization of early learning of a foreign language. The relevance of this problem is caused by a number of factors. Early learning of foreign languages is, first of all, a play activity aimed at the development and upbringing of the child, it is a way of socializing the child, revealing the child's potential, taking into account his individual characteristics. Secondly, this is connected not so much with the development of pedagogy and teaching methods of various disciplines and subjects, but with fashion trends and trends among parents. Nevertheless, the problem of early learning has been considered for several centuries and is being actively studied by modern scientists: psychologists, teachers, and methodologists.

Early learning contributes to the fulfillment of important methodological tasks:

- Creating children's psychological readiness for verbal communication;
- Ensuring the natural need for them to repeat language material multiple times;
- Training students in choosing the right speech option, which is preparation for learning English.

The issue of early teaching of foreign languages arose in the 19th century. It was then that the methodology of early teaching of foreign languages began to emerge as a branch of

methodological science. At this time, in no other country in the world was the experience of teaching foreign languages to children as widespread as in Russia. According to contemporaries, in Russia in the 19th century it was possible to meet a child who spoke three foreign languages fluently: French, English, and German. The education of 5-10 year old children from the wealthy classes was widespread.

In a modern, dynamically developing society, trends towards internationalization and integration of various spheres of human activity are increasingly visible. Today, the development of diverse relations with other countries has made the language really in demand by society.

An early start in learning a foreign language has become one of the priorities in the practice of teaching the subject. Currently, in many preschool educational institutions and various centers, children from an early age are introduced to a foreign language. Integrative classes provide additional opportunities for the versatile education of a preschooler, for the development of not only language, but also general abilities.

The problem of early teaching of foreign languages is reflected in a number of scientific works of domestic and foreign researchers and methodologists, such as V.N. Meshcheryakova, N.V. Semenova, I.N. Pavlenko, I.L. Sholpo, Z.Ya. Futerman, L.P. Gusev, N.A. Gorlova, M.A. Khasanova, Carol Read, Cristiana Bruni, Diana Webster and others.[1]

The leading goal of early learning of foreign languages is, first of all, a developmental goal. Teaching foreign languages to preschool children is designed to help protect and strengthen the physical and mental health of children and the development of their individual abilities. Therefore, the main goal of education is the personal development of the child through the means of the subject. This goal is strategic; it allows you to organically include a foreign language in the context of a preschooler's life and determine specific ways to implement integrative connections between the subject and other types and forms of activity of a preschool child.[1]

The implementation of this goal includes:

- 1) Development of the child's language abilities (memory, speech hearing, attention, etc.);
- 2) Introducing the child to the language and culture of another people and forming a positive attitude towards them; children's awareness of their native culture;
- 3) Fostering in the child a sense of self-awareness as an individual belonging to a particular linguistic and cultural community;
- 4) Development of the child's mental, emotional, creative qualities, his imagination, ability for social interaction, joy of learning and curiosity;[8]

By learning poems and songs in a foreign language, listening and dramatizing fairy tales of other people, getting acquainted with the games played by their peers abroad, carrying out this or that activity, children master a communicative minimum sufficient to carry out foreign language communication at an elementary level. We are talking about the formation of practical skills in oral foreign language speech, namely:

- skills in typical situations of everyday communication and within the framework of the lexical and grammatical material designated by the program, to understand oral foreign language speech and respond to it both verbally and non-verbally;
- skills in direct communication with a person speaking a foreign language;

- carry out their speech and non-speech behavior in accordance with the rules of communication and the national and cultural characteristics of the country of the language being studied.

The main educational, developmental and educational goals are as follows:

- in developing in children a positive attitude towards the activities performed and interest in the language being studied, in the culture of the people speaking this language;
- in nurturing moral qualities of students: a sense of duty, responsibility, collectivism, tolerance and respect for each other;
- in the development of preschoolers' mental functions (memory, attention, imagination, voluntary actions), cognitive abilities (verbal logical thinking, awareness of linguistic phenomena), and emotional sphere;
- in expanding the general educational horizons of children.[10]

The educational objectives are as follows:

- in the formation of skills and abilities to independently solve basic communicative problems in a foreign language;
- in the formation of interpersonal communication skills and self-control skills;
- in acquiring basic linguistic and cultural knowledge.

In addition, one of the most important psychological tasks of early learning foreign languages is the formation of a positive attitude towards learning a new language, as well as the creation of internal interest in children at every moment of learning.

The question of the child's ability to master foreign languages is very exciting for parents and important for teachers. Are there specific abilities in this area, and if so, how are they related to other personality traits, and can they be corrected? Is it possible to talk about linguistic giftedness, as we talk about musical or literary giftedness?

The following components of linguistic abilities are distinguished:

- pronounced verbal memory;
- speed and ease of formation of functional-linguistic generalizations;
- imitation speech abilities at the phonetic, lexical, grammatical and stylistic levels;
- the ability to quickly master a new psycholinguistic angle of view on objects of the objective world when moving from one language to another;
- ability to formalize verbal material.

These not entirely clear formulations are rightly criticized by A.A. Leontyev, who puts forward a rather bold statement that there are no "language abilities" at all as such.

"In general, language abilities are made up... of many components, most often nonspecific, unspecialized," the scientist believes. To such nonspecific abilities A.A. Leontiev refers to the general type of nervous system, temperament, character, individual differences in the course of mental processes (memory, thinking, perception, imagination), as well as individual personality characteristics associated with communication.[4]

I.L. Sholpo completely agrees with A.A. Leontiev, who claims that "there are no restrictions, called 'nature', on the child's capabilities."

However, I.L. Sholpo believes that it is still possible to talk about some specific language abilities; thus, she identifies the following main parameters by which one can judge whether a person is more or less gifted in the field of learning foreign languages:

- Speech hearing, which involves sensitivity to the phonetic, rhythmic and intonation aspects of speech.

- Language memory, which allows you to quickly expand your vocabulary, master new forms and grammatical structures, and translate words from a passive vocabulary to an active one.

- Lexical sense, which allows you to connect the meaning of a word and its form, draw parallels with other languages, feel the meaning of individual word-forming suffixes and prefixes, determine shades of meaning when choosing the necessary word from a synonymous row, etc.

- Grammatical (constructive) sense, which makes it possible to create a harmonious whole from disparate elements, to feel the commonality of grammatical structures, to isolate the grammatical core, to determine methods of forming and coordinating words in a sentence.

- Emotional-figurative perception of language, including a subjective assessment of the word, a sense of "taste", the originality of a given language, its beauty, ensuring the connection between the word and the concept, filling verbal abstraction with life.

- Functional-stylistic perception of language, which involves distinguishing its stylistic layers and the ability to evaluate a specific speech situation from this point of view.

Important nonspecific personality traits that are necessary for successful mastery of a foreign language are the presence of a positive attitude, interest in the life and culture of different countries, as a general manifestation of an active interest in the world, as well as personal sociability, that is, the desire and ability to communicate with other people and the ability to easily adapt to different communication situations.[5]

In order to identify the level of development of linguistic abilities, you can use simple testing.

It is necessary to conclude that language abilities, like any other, develop only in appropriate activities and therefore "any normal child can and should master a foreign language and use it freely in communication" (Leontyev A.A.), but it will happen whether this is true or not largely depends on the organization of his activities by the teacher, on the methodological approach to teaching.

L.S. Vygotsky and D.B. Elkonin call play the leading activity of a preschooler, but scientists do not mean that it predominates in his practice among all other types of activity, but that it is she who leads the development of the preschooler during this period.

Despite the fact that a lot has already been written about children's play, its theoretical issues are so complex that a unified classification of games still does not exist. I.L. Sholpo offers her own version of the classification of educational games that can be used in foreign language classes with preschoolers.

He divides educational games into situational, competitive, rhythmic-musical and artistic.

Situational games include role-playing games that simulate communication situations on a particular occasion.

Most games that promote the acquisition of vocabulary and literacy are competitive. These are all kinds of crosswords, auctions, board games with linguistic tasks, command execution, etc.[9]

Rhythm-musical games are all kinds of traditional games such as round dances, songs and dances with a choice of partners, for example: "Nuts and May".

Artistic, or creative, games are a type of activity that stands on the border of play and artistic creativity, the path to which lies for the child through games (staging small scenes in

English; visual games, such as graphic dictation, appliqué; verbal and creative (selection of rhymes, collective writing of captions for comics, collective writing of small fairy tales).

On the border of situational improvisational games and creative dramatization there is such a type of activity as improvisation on the theme of a well-known fairy tale, which has already been played in an established form. For example, a game of "Turnip" or "Teremok", in which, depending on the number of players and the acquisition of new vocabulary, new characters and lines appear.

"1. Before you start playing, answer the following questions:

What is the purpose of the game, what should the child learn in it?

What speech action should he perform: one of... actions with a word or the creation of a statement - then which one exactly and according to what model?

Does the child know how to construct such a statement, are there any additional difficulties or pitfalls?

2. After answering these questions, try to turn into a child yourself and come up with an interesting situation in which a statement based on such a model could arise.

3. Think about how to describe this situation to the child in such a way that he immediately accepts it...

4. Have fun playing with your child yourself! "

This passage takes into account the main qualities of an educational game, which are noted in its very name: it must be educational and it must be a game. The Soviet encyclopedic dictionary defines play as a type of unproductive activity, the motive of which lies not in its result, but in the process itself. This is a very important sign. Therefore, when introducing a game into a lesson, its didactic result is important for the teacher, but cannot be an incentive for children's activities. The game should change the very style of relationship between children and the adult teacher, who cannot impose anything: a child can play only when he wants it and when it is interesting to him, and with those who evoke his sympathy. The teacher cannot only be the organizer of the game - he must play together with the child, because children play with adults with great pleasure and because the game atmosphere is destroyed under the gaze of an outside observer.[10]

Thus, an educational game is a game focused on the zone of proximal development, combining a pedagogical goal with an activity motive that is attractive to the child.

Let us turn once again to the data of developmental psychology.

"The essence of children's play is to play some role and to create some new position," wrote J. Selley. D.B. Elkonin considered the role and the actions associated with it to be the central point of the game.

Thus, we can say that the basis of any game is role-playing. In a role-playing game, a child can act as himself, an English child or an adult, a fairy-tale character or animal, an animated object, etc. - the possibilities here are unlimited.

His partner can be another child, a teacher, a doll, an imaginary character, an assistant actor, or a second teacher who always plays the same role, etc.

Summarizing all of the above, we can draw the following conclusions:

The methodology for conducting classes should be built taking into account the age and individual characteristics of the structure of children's linguistic abilities and be aimed at their development.

Foreign language classes must be comprehended by the teacher.

Teaching preschoolers a foreign language should be communicative in nature.

Communication in a foreign language must be motivated and focused. It is necessary to create in the child a positive psychological attitude toward foreign language speech.[12]

A way to create such positive motivation is through play.

Games in the classroom should not be episodic and isolated. An end-to-end gaming methodology is needed that combines and integrates other types of activities in the process of language learning.

The gaming technique is based on the creation of an imaginary situation and the adoption by the child or teacher of a particular role.

From the very beginning of training, it is necessary to develop a certain style of working with children in English, to introduce some kind of rituals that correspond to the most typical communication situations. Such rituals (greetings, farewells, short exercises, the use of politeness formulas accepted in English) allow children to prepare for foreign language communication, facilitate the transition to English, show children that the lesson has begun, has ended, and that a certain stage of the lesson will now follow.

The most important condition for successful learning is the activation of children's speech and thinking activity and their involvement in foreign language communication. It is necessary to constantly change the order of speech actions (the order of questions, addresses, names of objects, etc.) so that children react to the meaning of the word, and do not memorize the sound series mechanically. When repeating games, it is imperative to make different children the leading, active participants, so that all children perform the speech action provided for by the educational task at least once.[11]

To prevent fatigue and loss of interest in children, the teacher should conduct games with elements of movement and commands in English every 5-7 minutes of class.

If classes are held in a kindergarten group, with the entire group of children, then a serious difficulty arises: how to organize the game so that 5-7 people play, and the rest watch carefully, without being distracted. Here it is important to give the teacher some recommendations:

- change presenters more often so that others are interested in following the game: they understand that at any moment they will be among the players;
 - ask children to help players if they cannot cope with a game task;
 - ask the children to evaluate the players' actions in chorus (yes, no, right, wrong);
- “theatricalize” the situation as much as possible so that children watch with interest how it ends.

Conclusion

Thus, early teaching of a foreign language to children has a positive effect on the formation of both linguistic and general culture. It can be a good motivation for learning your native language. Learning takes place in an artificial language environment. During classes, phonemic hearing, visual and auditory memory, touch and even smell, memory for taste, development of attention, thinking and speech develop. Efficiency is achieved by integrating various types of activities (game, subject, speech, etc.) with real activities (all routine moments, reading books, etc.). During classes, the child develops linguistic abilities, taking into account age-related characteristics..

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